

ON STRUCTURE OF SEMIGROUPS OF LINKED UPFAMILIES

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In the talk we shall discuss the algebraic structure of extension $N(X)$ of a semigroup X . A family \mathcal{F} of subsets of a set X is called an *upfamily* if each set $F \in \mathcal{F}$ is not empty and for each set $F \in \mathcal{F}$ any subset $E \supset F$ of X belongs to \mathcal{F} . The space of all upfamilies on X is denoted by $v(X)$. It is a closed subspace of the double power-set $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{P}(X))$ endowed with the compact Hausdorff topology of the Tychonoff product $\{0, 1\}^{\mathcal{P}(X)}$. Identifying each point $x \in X$ with the upfamily $\langle x \rangle = \{A \subset X : x \in A\}$, we can identify X with a subspace of $v(X)$. Because of that we call $v(X)$ an extension of X .

The compact Hausdorff space $v(X)$ contains many other important extensions of X as closed subspaces. In particular, it contains the space $N(X)$ of linked upfamilies on X , see [1]. Let us recall that an upfamily $\mathcal{F} \in v(X)$ is called a *linked* if $A \cap B \neq \emptyset$ for any $A, B \in \mathcal{F}$.

In [2] it was observed that any (associative) binary operation $*$: $X \times X \rightarrow X$ can be extended to an (associative) binary operation $*$: $v(X) \times v(X) \rightarrow v(X)$ defined by the formula:

$$\mathcal{A} * \mathcal{B} = \left\langle \bigcup_{a \in \mathcal{A}} a * B_a : \mathcal{A} \in \mathcal{A}, \{B_a\}_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \subset \mathcal{B} \right\rangle$$

for upfamilies $\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B} \in v(X)$. Here for a family \mathcal{C} of non-empty subsets of X by

$$\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle = \{A \subset X : \exists C \in \mathcal{C} \text{ with } C \subset A\}$$

we denote the upfamily generated by the family \mathcal{C} .

According to [2], for each semigroup X , $v(X)$ is a compact Hausdorff right-topological semigroup containing the subspace $N(X)$ as closed subsemigroup. We study right and left zeros, idempotents, the minimal ideal, left cancellable and right cancellable elements of the semigroup $N(X)$ of linked upfamilies on X and characterize groups X whose extensions $N(X)$ are commutative, see [3].

1. Gavrylkiv V. The spaces of inclusion hyperspaces over noncompact spaces. *Mat. Stud.*, 2007, **28**, no. 1, P. 92–110.
2. Gavrylkiv V. Right-topological semigroup operations on inclusion hyperspaces. *Mat. Stud.*, 2008, **29**, no. 1, P. 18–34.
3. Gavrylkiv V. Semigroups of linked upfamilies, *PVNTSh: Number*, 2015, 9 p.